

Chromatographic Study of Anionic Complexes. Part XI. Some Ionophoretic Studies on Metal Ions in presence of Citrate and Tartrate as Complexants

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Ionophoretic studies on the migration of Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Ni^{2+} have shown that in presence of citrate these form anionic complexes in a neutral and alkaline media (*pH* above 7). The stoichiometry of metal: ligand is 1:1 in the case of Cu (π), Ni (π), and Co (π) and 1:2 for Zn (π), obtained by the progressive addition of the complexant to the metal ion and subjecting the solution to the study of electrophoresis to determine the nature of the charge acquired by the complex.

Electrophoretic migrations of Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} in presence of tartrate show that these also form 1:1 complexes above *pH* 7.

In earlier communications¹, the migration of cations forming anionic complexes has been studied in presence of oxalate, citrate, and tartrate. The authors also reported some separations of bivalent and trivalent metal ions in presence and absence of citrate² added as a complexant.

In the present communication, the ionophoretic movement of some cations has been investigated with the progressive amounts of added citrate or tartrate as a complexant at different hydrogen-ion concentrations. Attempts have also been made to utilise the results in the elucidation of the composition of the complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

LKB (type 3276B) paper electrophoresis equipment was employed, using Pt anode and steel cathode. A power supply unit of the same manufacture (type 3290B) was used, which operated on 220V/50 cycles a. c. mains.

Metal solutions were prepared from reagent grade chemicals and standardised by the usual methods. Standard solutions of HNO_3 and KOH were prepared from B. D. H. AnalaR chemicals. Carl Schleicher and Schull No. 2043 filter papers, 120g./m² of size 40 × 410 mm, were employed.

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1. Singh and Dey, *this Journal*, 1961, **38**, 193; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, **20B**, 388; *J. Chromatog.*, 1959 **2**, 95; 1960, **3**, 146; *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1961, **178**, 356.
2. Bobtelsky *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 1830; *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1951, 494.
3. Biswas and Dey, *this Journal*, 1965, **42**, 275.

Procedure.—Progressive amounts of sodium citrate or potassium tartrate were added separately to the test tubes containing 1 ml of the metal solution and the total volume was raised to 5 ml in each case. These mixtures were spotted separately on the paper, previously marked with a pin point, and subjected to electrophoresis, using a mixture of 0.01M-HNO₃ and 0.01M-KOH as the background electrolyte, prepared by mixing these two components at different ratios to obtain a desired pH value. After 1 hr., these were developed with a suitable reagent to ascertain the nature of the ions. The ratios of the ligand: metal, required to produce an anionic complex, are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Ratio of metal to ligand required for the formation of anionic citrate and tartrate complexes.

Voltage = 6.1 V/cm. Time = 60 min. Electrolyte = 0.01M-HNO₃ + 0.01M-KOH.

Reagents : Cu (II) : 0.1% w/v rubeanic acid in EtOH.

Zn (II) : 0.1 ,, dithizone in CCl₄.

Co (II) : 0.5 ,, α -nitroso- β -naphthol.

Ni (II) : 1.0 ,, dimethylglyoxime in EtOH.

Metal complex.	pH.	Ratio of metal : ligand.
Cu(II)—citrate	3.0	1 : 2
	5.0	1 : 1.5
	7.0	1 : 1
	9.0	1 : 1
Zn(II)—citrate	3.0	1 : 4
	5.0	1 : 4
	7.0	1 : 3
	9.0	1 : 2
Co(II)—citrate	3.0	1 : 2
	5.0	1 : 2
	7.0	1 : 1
	9.0	1 : 1
Ni(II)—citrate	3.0	1 : 2
	5.0	1 : 1.5
	7.0	1 : 1
	9.0	1 : 1
Cu(II)—tartrate	3.0	..
	5.0	..
	7.0	1 : 1
	9.0	1 : 1
Ni(II)—tartrate	3.0	..
	5.0	..
	7.0	1 : 1
	9.0	1 : 1

The studies on the metal-citrate and -tartrate complexes were carried out using background electrolytes of different pH values. The ratio Me^{nt}: ligand required to produce an anionic complex ion was found to depend on the hydrogen-ion concentration of the back-

ground electrolyte, as shown in Table I. The results show that the formation of citrate and tartrate complexes is facilitated in a neutral and alkaline media, where the composition of the complex is revealed. By such a study, the formation of the complex could be guessed by the alteration of the migration of ion from cathodic to anodic, as shown, for example, in Table II.

TABLE II

System: Cu^{2+} - K_2tart - H_2O .

<i>pH</i> of the background electrolyte.	Ratio $\text{Cu (II)} : \text{K}_2 \text{ tart.}$	‡ Change of the spot from cationic to anionic distance travelled (mm).
3.0	1 : 0.0	+45
	1 : 0.5	+45
	1 : 1.0	+45
	1 : 1.5	+45
	1 : 2.0	+44
5.0	1 : 0.0	+45
	1 : 0.5	+42
	1 : 1.0	+42
	1 : 1.5	+42
	1 : 2.0	+42
7.0	1 : 0.0	+45
	1 : 0.5	+10
	1 : 1.0	-25
	1 : 1.5	-25
	1 : 2.0	-24
9.0	1 : 0.0	+45
	1 : 0.5	+10
	1 : 1.0	-25
	1 : 1.5	-25
	1 : 2.0	-24

The compositions of the citrate complexes therefore are $(\text{CuCit})^{1-}$, $(\text{ZnCit}_2)^{4-}$, $(\text{CoCit})^{1-}$, and $(\text{NiCit})^{1-}$ above *pH* 7, corroborating the results obtained by Bobtelsky *et al.*². In the case of tartrate complexes, no formation of anionic complexes takes place in an acidic medium and the formation of 1:1 complexes of Ni (II) and Cu (II) are indicated in a neutral and an alkaline medium. Thus these complexes of bivalent metal ions are neutralised by 1 equivalent of alkali at *pH* 6—9, as though these were monobasic acids. The H^+ of one hydroxyl group is labilised by the co-ordination link of the oxygen to the metal. Hence

‡ + indicates cationic and —, anionic.

in an alkaline medium these are converted into anions, exemplified by tartrate system with 4-co-ordination number and 6-co-ordination number of Me (II) with ligand.

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